

<03/06/2022>

Submission of comments on

‘THE FINAL EVALUATION OF THE THIRD HEALTH PROGRAMME 2014-2020’

Public Consultation from the European Commission

Comments from:

Name of organisation or individual

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy and Dr Éloïse Gennet on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw and the I-BioLex research project

Please find below the answer to the public consultation on ‘the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation’ by **Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy** (*CNRS Permanent researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l’Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*), and **Dr Éloïse Gennet** (*Post-doctoral researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l’Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*) **on behalf of the Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw from the European Association of Health Law (EAHL) and the I-BioLex research project.**

The EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw is co-chaired by Aurélie Mahalatchimy (UMR 7318 DICE CERIC, CNRS, Aix Marseille University, France) and Mark

Flear (Queen’s University Belfast, UK) and involved legal experts in Supranational Biolaw, mainly academics, from 14 EU member States, the UK and Switzerland.

The [EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw](#) has been created in 2020 within the European Association of Health Law. It aims to promote European health law, especially in its European-level dimension, regarding the law and the various legal issues arising from technological advances related to medicine and biotechnology. Among its activities, it mobilises its members to address demands from several groups within society, including legislators and regulators, scientists (researchers and clinicians), and patients regarding Supranational Biolaw. The EAHL IG on Supranational Biolaw is also the leader of one of the 2021 Thematic Network of the European Union Health Policy Platform. The Thematic Network is entitled “Health as a fundamental value. Towards an equitable and inclusive pharmaceutical strategy for the EU”.

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy and Dr Éloïse Gennet provides this answer on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw.

The I-BioLex project “Fragmentation and defragmentation of the law on biomedical innovations” is funded by the French National Agency for Research (ANR-20-CE26-0007-01, coord. A. Mahalatchimy; 2021-2024). [I-BioLex](#) is exploring whether the processes of fragmentation (division or segmentation), and defragmentation (gathering together, connecting or ‘harmonising’) can jointly contribute to and express the adaptability and coherence of the law as it pertains to Biomedical innovations (BI), in areas such as gene therapy, regenerative medicine, or nanomedicine. Building on the works linked to legal oversight of complex BI, law temporality and law fragmentation phenomenon, I-BioLex uses comparative and interdisciplinary approaches and combines theoretical and empirical elements to test this hypothesis while helping to determine how the law on BI can serve diverse societal objectives. Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy and Dr Éloïse Gennet provides this answer on behalf of the I-BioLex Research project.

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy and Dr Éloïse Gennet are grateful to the European Commission to have been given the opportunity to contribute to this consultation.

Please see below our additional comments.

Several questions (from 30 to 35) are too oriented towards expected answers as it seems obvious that the 3rd Health Programme's specific objectives are very relevant EU health needs and that the 3rd Health Programme priorities are all very relevant.

Question 42 appears too ambiguous to allow a satisfactory answer. If we answer that the costs associated with the 3rd Health Programme are not at all reasonable and kept to the minimum necessary in order to achieve the expected results, it may involve that they are either too low or too high.

For question 44, the system did not allow to select three criteria as provided.

The three EU added value criteria we consider the most important are:

- Supporting networks for knowledge sharing or mutual learning
- Unlocking the potential of innovation in health

- Improving efficiency by avoiding waste of resources due to duplication and optimising use of financial resources